

IPv6 Connection Shuffling for Moving Target Defense (MTD) in SDN

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Abstract—Moving Target Defense (MTD) is the defensive strategy of obscuring an entity by controlled changes in its attack surface. This approach alone does not secure a system but challenges potential attacks with additional complexity. This work presents an MTD solution called “Randomized Host and Service Shuffling in IPv6 (RHSS6)” against network reconnaissance attacks and evaluates its effects on performance and security. To achieve this goal, a Software Defined Networking (SDN) based prototype was developed in which RHSS6 performs two MTD strategies, IP Shuffling and Port Shuffling. Measurements on TCP and UDP traffic are made to evaluate the performance impact of RHSS6. An MTD network with both IP Shuffling and Port Shuffling had similar performance results compared to a baseline network; however, the video stream bit rate was significantly lower when Port Shuffling was enforced. Regarding the security gain, RHSS6 was effective in increasing the average number of scan attempts needed to identify a targeted host in a network with a fixed address range. We conclude that a defender using RHSS6 can adjust the probability of an attacker locating targeted hosts in a network by selecting a suitable address space and port range. Such parameters and shuffling trigger time can be optimized to maximize the benefits for different scenarios while minimizing the operational overhead.

I. INTRODUCTION

The number of software and hardware vulnerabilities per year is rising consistently, and the number of observed cyber-attacks is expected to surge in future networks such as 6G or NextG systems [1]. To reduce the likelihood of successful exploitation of these vulnerabilities, defensive principles, like the Defense in Depth (DiD), become more relevant. The DiD approach is a security strategy that uses multiple layers of security measures to protect a system or a network. If one layer of defense is compromised or fails, additional layers mitigate the impact and prevent further compromise. One way to implement a DiD approach is to implement the MTD strategy, which adds complexity to the attacker’s tasks [2], [3]. The National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) defines MTD as: “The concept of controlling change across multiple system dimensions in order to increase uncertainty and apparent complexity for attackers, reduce their window of opportunity, and increase the costs of their probing and attack efforts” [4]. In that regard, MTD can be effective even against attackers who have already compromised or evaded the network-perimeter defense and have access to the links in the network forwarding paths [2].

As a defensive approach, connection shuffling serves the underlying paradigm of obfuscation and attack surface variability of MTD. Unfortunately, the communication overhead often increases with additional security mechanisms, including MTD shuffling techniques [2]. This phenomenon is an important factor regarding practical purposes. Furthermore, one can say that an IP address assignment scheme on a traditional network can already exhibit dynamicity due to the Dynamic Host Configuration Protocol (DHCP) or a Network Address Translation (NAT). However, these are not effective in providing proactive countermeasures because the IP mutation is infrequent and traceable [5]. Therefore, we propose an MTD solution based on SDN to address these aspects brought up in this work. Specifically, we introduce an MTD technique called *Randomized Host and Service Shuffling in IPv6 (RHSS6)* based on a combination of two shuffling techniques. Shuffling is a technique employed in MTD that alters specific attributes of nodes involved in network communication. This process enhances network security by introducing variability and, therefore, obfuscating the host’s identity. The shuffling process can be triggered through various means. The first strategy employed in RHSS6 is IP Shuffling, which involves altering the IP address of the protected host to modify its fingerprint. The second one is a port number shuffling technique that mimics a selection of specific protocols to another protocol¹.

Our contributions in this work are:

- RHSS6, a novel IP Shuffling and Port Shuffling technique using IPv6 addresses with SDN, and its open-source implementation.
- Analysis on how RHSS6 affects the success level of an attacker.
- Measurement of the security gain compared to the incurred overhead in this setting.
- Identification of limitations of such an approach when employed in various scenarios.

The remainder of this work is structured as follows. Section II presents related work on MTD and delineates key contributions of this work. Section III introduces the RHSS6 design and implementation, illustrating how the IP Shuffling and Port Shuffling techniques work. Section IV provides the perfor-

¹In this work, “IP Shuffling” and “Port Shuffling” are used as short names for “IP Address Shuffling” and “Port Number Shuffling”, respectively.

mance evaluation of RHSS6 based on different metrics and describes the experimental setup as well as procedures used to evaluate the performance and effectiveness of RHSS6. While Section V discusses security gains brought by RHSS6, Section VI concludes with a discussion and research directions.

II. RELATED WORK

This section discusses MTD techniques using IP Shuffling or Port Shuffling. Table I overviews the most significant differences between related work and our proposed approach.

IP Randomization: Jafarian et al. [5] proposed OpenFlow Random Host Mutation (OF-RHM) based on IPv4 addresses, which implements a shuffling technique that keeps the real IP addresses of hosts unchanged but assigns a random virtual IP address for each host inside the network. OF-RHM is implemented on Mininet as an OpenFlow-based SDN solution that selects randomly chosen IP addresses based on their weight. Every time a currently unused IP address is scanned, its weight increases by one, since an already scanned IP is less likely to be scanned again by an attacker [5]. The interval in which virtual IP addresses are changed depends on the total size of the allocated address range inside the specific subnet. This work is especially security-oriented, focusing on worm and external scanner threats. For the external scan, an IPv4 class B network with 2^{10} possible hosts was used. Not more than 1% of the IP addresses to protect have been discovered by the attacker. Overhead is briefly addressed based on the flow table size, but performance-relevant measurements, like the effective bandwidth, have not been reported.

IP Randomization and Port Hopping: Sharma et al. [6] proposed Random Host and Service Multiplexing (RHSM) using IPv4, which uses an IP Shuffling and Port Shuffling technique to hide the legitimate hosts inside the network. They use a multiplexing method, where multiple virtual IP addresses and virtual ports are used for the host’s communication with each other. The implementation was built on an SDN network. Their attack model assumes that the attacker exists outside the SDN. Their work aligns with the focus of the work in [5]. Overhead is based on the flow table size. The focus is on the domain of IP address and port-based scanners, mirroring a thematic parallel with our work. Luo et al. [7] proposed Random Port and Address Hopping (RPAH) based on IPv4, which deploys an IP Shuffling and Port Shuffling technique to create obfuscation so that an attacker cannot easily locate a target system. However, it had been deployed for traditional networks, and, therefore, SDN was not used. The host’s IP address and port dynamically change through a pseudo-random function that incorporates a secret key, the source’s identity, the type of service, and a timestamp as input variables. The attack model contains internal and external adversaries as well as internal and external network scanners, SYN flooding attacks, and worm propagation. However, the resulting scan success rate of nearly 0% is overly optimistic. In addition, the focus is on performance based on throughput and latency measurements. Notably, RHSS6 emerges as the superior performer when assessed in terms of performance.

TABLE I
COMPARISON OF RELATED WORK (I-S: IP SHUFFLING, P-S: PORT SHUFFLING, PoC: PROOF OF CONCEPT, S: SECURITY, P: PERFORMANCE).

Work	I-S	P-S	Deployed PoC	IP vers.	Network type	Analysis
[5]	✓	✗	✓	IPv4	SDN	S
[6]	✓	✓	✗	IPv4	SDN	S
[7]	✓	✓	✓	IPv4	trad.	S + P
[8]	✓	✓	✓	IPv4	trad.	S + P
RHSS6	✓	✓	✓	IPv6	SDN	S + P

This difference in performance can be attributed to the fact that RPAH was evaluated on traditional network infrastructure involving hosts located outside the LAN, as opposed to the more performance-enhanced SDN environment.

Luo et al. [8] proposed the Test Access Point (TAP) based Port and Address Hopping (TPAH) based on IPv4, which is similar to RPAH. TPAH is carried out within a universal virtual-network kernel driver TAP for a general and multi-platform deployable port and address hopping mechanism [8]. It implements the IP address and port selection as an output of a pseudo-random function and is based on time-synchronization, while its input consists of the shared secret key, time, port, and address variance range. This work focuses on the detection and mitigation of port scanning and Denial of Service (DoS) attacks. Furthermore, it conducts latency measurements to assess the performance. Compared RHSS6 to TPAH, RHSS6 stands out as the solution with the better performance in terms of latency. The improved performance of RHSS6 can be attributed to the utilization of an SDN environment. The performance-wise significant difference of TPAH and RPAH is that hosts in TPAH reside in the same LAN environment as the MTD environment.

Based on the literature review, no prior work has thoroughly dealt with IPv6 addresses in the context of combined connection shuffling techniques for MTD in an SDN network to increase the level of security, which also takes the overall performance of the system into consideration. Furthermore, the unique evaluation of incorporating both IP Shuffling and Port Shuffling offers novel insights into the security and performance aspects of the system. In contrast to those algorithms presented in related work, algorithms proposed in our work incorporate ICMPv6 packets, which is an integral part of the functionality of IPv6 [9], and use the enlarged address space of IPv6 to extend the IP Shuffling range. The shuffling algorithm of OF-RHM incorporates DNS packets, and RPAH makes use of an Access Control List (ACL). The RHSS6 algorithm deployed omits the usage of DNS packets or an ACL, leading to simplicity and less dependency. Nevertheless, it does not provide the newly shuffled virtual IP addresses and ports to hosts attempting to communicate with those protected by RHSS6.

III. RHSS6 DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION

In our threat model, we assume that the attacker can access the targeted network by sending packets. Beyond this

Fig. 1. RHSS6 operation.

capability, the attacker does not possess any other advanced capacities. Consequently, network traffic analysis attacks are not considered.

RHSS6 is divided into two main components that also work independently. IP Shuffling masks the real IPv6 address of protected clients with a virtual IPv6 address that changes in a set interval. All communication addressing the actual address is dropped to force the use of the virtual address. Port Shuffling switches the protocol header of packets in a fixed interval to mask the protocol used by an application. Figure 1 shows a typical UDP packet flow with Host 4 (H4) addressing the protected Host 1 (H1):

1. H4 sends a UDP request with the destination IP as the virtual IP of H1 and with the destination port of the virtual port of H1.

2. The destination address and port are switched from the virtual IP and port of H1 to the real IP and port of H1 by the switch S1.

3. H1 sends a UDP response with its real IP and port as source IP and port to H4.

4. The source IP and port are switched from the real IP and port of H1 to the virtual IP and port of H1 by the switch S1.

Algorithm 1 shows how the controller handles unknown packets. The full code is implemented in Python and uses Mininet with Ryu as the SDN controller. The code is available on the RHSS6 GitHub repository².

IV. PERFORMANCE RESULTS

Section IV-A introduces the experiments and measurements used and highlights their relevance for the evaluation of RHSS6. Section IV-B presents experimental results and analyzes the RHSS6's network overhead in case studies.

A. Experiments and Measurements

The measurements were done following the network topology shown in Figure 1. The experiments were carried out with different numbers of client-server (C-S) pairs, with the servers

Algorithm 1 Packet Handling for Shuffling

```

Require:  $packet.type = TCP|UDP|ICMP$ 
 $hdr = pkt.hdr$ 
if  $hdr.dst.ip$  in  $getRealIPs()$  or  $hdr.dst.port$  in  $getRealPorts()$  then
  drop packet
end if
if  $hdr.dst.ip$  in  $getVirtIPs()$  then
   $hdr.dst.ip = getRealIP(hdr.dst.ip)$ 
end if
if  $hdr.src.ip$  in  $getRealIPs()$  then
   $hdr.src.ip = getVirtIP(hdr.src.ip)$ 
end if
if  $hdr.dst.port$  in  $getVirtPorts()$  then
   $hdr.dst.port = getRealPort(hdr.dst.port)$ 
end if
if  $hdr.src.port$  in  $getRealPorts()$  then
   $hdr.src.port = getVirtPort(hdr.src.port)$ 
end if
 $addFlow(pkt)$ 

```

acting as the hosts performing connection shuffling for MTD. The underlying SDN infrastructure runs on an Ubuntu VM with 32GB of RAM and 16 vCPU cores at 2 GHz clock speed from an AMD EPYC CPU. The goal of this work is to investigate the performance in a restricted context to identify key characteristics.

For the assessment of various performance aspects by employing different commands, namely `iperf3` and `ping`, and by leveraging the Dynamic Adaptive Streaming over HTTP (DASH) protocol [10] (*cf.* Section IV-B1), the Round Trip Time (RTT) and bit rate metrics are employed. The performance evaluation was conducted 10 times for each metric, and mean values were calculated to account for variances arising from the characteristics of the network infrastructure. The shuffling process occurs only once during the startup when receiving the client's connection request.

The tool `iperf3` was used to create streams inside the SDN infrastructure and measure the overall bandwidth of TCP and UDP connections for different numbers of hosts. To ensure consistent results, both TCP and UDP connections were conducted at a fixed bitrate of 2 Gbps, thereby minimizing potential variations in UDP performance. Each `iperf3` run lasted 200 s. To ensure proper initialization of `iperf3`, the analysis did not consider the first 100 s of each evaluation run. This approach allowed sufficient time for `iperf3` to stabilize and provide accurate performance measurements.

With the `iperf3` traffic running in the background, the RTT was measured using the `ping` command being run continuously for 100 s. The average latency over this duration was used for comparison. To conduct practical performance measurements at the application layer, the DASH streaming protocol was utilized along with the GPAC tool, again with the `iperf3` traffic running on the background. GPAC creates streaming-ready files from media content and provides an integrated client for viewing and analyzing the streamed media [11]. The media to be streamed is a 7-minute-long video placed on one of the servers acting as a Web server [12]. The client then connects to the Web server, which sends the stream data with the additional meta files to the client.

²RHSS6 Project link: <https://github.com/mtd-recon/mtd-recon>

³iperf3 tool: <https://iperf.fr/>

Fig. 2. iperf3 TCP evaluation with 1, 4, and 100 servers (each with the corresponding number of clients)

B. Performance Evaluation

1) *Performance Overview*: The TCP and UDP columns in Table II are generally coherent, but an interesting observation is that the RTT values decrease as the number of active iperf streams increases (*blue highlighted*). One possible reason for this is the CPU scheduler’s optimization, which reduces context switches and therefore prioritizes the OVS forwarding process over other processes. It is also visible that the overall iperf3 bit rate for the UDP case performs better than TCP if the load on the system does not rise.

There is a significant decrease in the DASH video stream’s quality in Table II, for case *8S - 8C* when compared to case *1S - 1C* and *4S - 4C*. This is due to the fact that the load on the system with sixteen vCPU cores rises due to the number of iperf3 sessions and therefore the DASH video stream performance decreases. Consequently, unpredictable behavior of the performance arises, which can also be seen on the iperf3 bit rate values for the *8S - 8C* case (*yellow highlighted*) and in Figure 2. The overhead of the proposed solution is minimal, as we assume that CPU scheduling is significantly more effective

TABLE II
PERFORMANCE MEASUREMENTS FOR RHSS6 (C: CLIENT, S: SERVER.
THE REPORTED BIT RATES ARE AVERAGE VALUES PER C-S PAIR).

Case	Mode	Ping RTT [ms]		DASH video stream bit rate [Mbps]		iperf3 bit rate [Gbps]	
		TCP ^a	UDP ^a	TCP ^a	UDP ^a	TCP	UDP
1S,1C	no MTD	0.0745	0.055	1295	1491	1.494	1.684
	IP	0.05	0.052	1450	1630	1.509	1.708
	port	0.051	0.055	159	285	1.402	1.781
	IP+port	0.055	0.051	147	266	1.392	1.583
4S,4C	no MTD	0.065	0.045	1545	1735	1.401	1.672
	IP	0.052	0.048	1588	1604	1.402	1.547
	port	0.051	0.054	213	324	1.409	1.517
	IP+port	0.045	0.053	237	313	1.419	1.542
8S,8C	no MTD	0.041	0.042	1350	1051	1.546	1.557
	IP	0.037	0.054	1078	1061	1.374	1.598
	port	0.041	0.036	493	486	1.502	1.465
	IP+port	0.038	0.052	421	421	1.416	1.542

^aThe TCP and UDP columns under “Ping RTT” and “DASH video stream” present the measurements with the TCP and UDP iperf3 traffic running simultaneously in the background.

in performance simulations. It is also evident that the Port Shuffling technique negatively influences the performance of the GPAC DASH video stream use case (*green highlighted*). This observed phenomenon might be due to the addition of an extra layer. In IP shuffling, only the L3 header (such as checksum) is altered. When port shuffling is active, the L4 header (including the L4 checksum and fragmentation) is also involved. Consequently, in a heavily loaded environment, this can significantly decrease performance.

2) *TCP / UDP Performance*: Regarding the TCP performance, the *no MTD* mode is, as expected, the most stable variant, which is visible in Figure 2⁴. In Figure 2, it is also visible that all modes have an increasing number of outliers because of the unpredictable behavior once the load of the system rises, as mentioned in IV-B1. The performance gap remains marginal when both IP Shuffling and Port Shuffling are implemented, compared to when only one of them is enforced. The results in Figure 2 with *100S - 100C* exhibit higher variations across all modes due to the presence of outliers. However, they also demonstrate similar performance levels for all modes, suggesting that the overhead of the MTD shuffling method is minimal when the system is subjected to elevated traffic (*i.e.*, iperf3 traffic in this case).

3) *Discussion on Results and Limitations*: Results show that the system performance reduction remains marginal when the number of iperf3 sessions rises. The top command also indicated that the overload was created by the iperf3 communication sessions and does not originate from processes that are not related to the SDN infrastructure. The characteristic of increased variability across all modes with rising load may not be suitable for practical applications that require stable

⁴UDP results share many similarities with their TCP counterparts and are, thus, omitted in Figure 2. These UDP figures are available on the project’s GitHub repository.

TABLE III
PARAMETERS USED IN SECTION V

Parameter	Definition
N_1	Average number of attempts needed to guess the address
N_2	Average number of attempts needed to guess the port
n	Number of addresses in the address space
m	Number of ports in the port range
I	Shuffling interval in seconds
S	Scanning rate (scans/seconds)
T	Time to guess the address/port in seconds
$P(X)$	Probability of guessing the correct address/port

network conditions with an increased number of network hosts, such as Internet of Things (IoT) systems or 5G/Beyond-5G networks providing a very wide range of ubiquitous services. However, various approaches can address this, especially a costly approach would be to increase available system resources so that the traffic inside the network can be increased without losing performance. Another approach would be to use the QoS REST functionality of Ryu to reserve network bandwidth for a particular communication in order to communicate with a constant bandwidth on the network. While these approaches, coupled with the deployment of additional SDN switches, have the potential to enhance stability and performance in real-world scenarios, a proof-of-concept is essential to validate their effectiveness. Overall, our main goal in this paper is not to investigate the optimal resource allocation/management regarding scalability for our scheme but to analyze the performance in a designated environment.

Another concern is the ‘‘Address Block Ownership’’. If the defender does not own an IPv6 block, they can use a purely local network if the hosts do not need an Internet connection. In the other case with an Internet connection, they can use a single address combined with NAT for IPv6, *e.g.*, NAT66.

V. SECURITY PROFILE OF RHSS6

To analyze the security impact of the scheme developed, both theoretical and simulated approaches are applied. The security is measured of the targeted system with no MTD, with only IP Shuffling, with only Port Shuffling, and with both MTD techniques combined. The parameters used in the formulas are listed in Table III.

Case 1: Undefended Network – We determine the average number of attempts required by an attacker to correctly guess addresses or ports in a non-MTD network as $N_1 = \frac{n}{2}$ and $N_2 = N_1 + \frac{m}{2}$.

In the context of port scanning, it is assumed that the port can only be identified once the IP address of the device is known. The time required for an attacker to make an accurate guess of the correct address is then $T = \frac{N_1}{S}$ for the average case and $T = \frac{n}{S}$ for the worst case. Similarly, the duration for an attacker to accurately guess the correct port is $T = \frac{N_2}{S}$ for the average case and $T = \frac{n}{S} + \frac{m}{S}$ for the worst case.

Case 2: Network with MTD – In the context of MTD, an additional metric is introduced and denoted as ‘‘z,’’ which

is calculated as the reciprocal of the number of shuffling operations performed during a scan. This quantity is defined by the following equation:

$$z = \frac{S * I}{n}$$

The likelihood of correctly guessing the IP address in an MTD network, where only IP Shuffling is implemented, is as follows:

$$P(X) = \sum_{y=1}^{\infty} z(1-z)^y$$

In this formula, y is defined as the current number of utilized full scans. The outcome of this formula will approximate to a value at which the probability of correctly guessing the address/port becomes confident, with the speed of convergence depending on z and y . To determine the average number of attempts required for an attacker to guess the address correctly, the following formulas are utilized:

$$N_1 = \frac{n}{P(X)} = n \quad \text{since} \quad P(X) = 1$$

The duration it takes for an attacker to guess the correct address successfully is:

$$\text{Average case: } T = \frac{N_1}{S} \quad \text{and} \quad \text{Worst case: } T = \text{Never}$$

These calculations are based on the assumption that a single source address is utilized for scanning. However, when multiple sources are involved in scanning, the necessary number of attempts also becomes valid. Nonetheless, the scanning durations should be divided by the number of sources involved.

A. Numerical Evaluations

The simulation code to verify $P(X)$ and its results can be found in the RHSS6 GitHub repository. In this context, $P(X)$ equals 1 when z falls within the range of 0 to 1 ($0 < z < 1$), which is the case for shuffling. Consequently, it appears that shuffling effectively doubles the value of N_1 compared to the scenario without MTD. Given that Port Shuffling operates on similar principles, the combination of IP Shuffling and Port Shuffling results in a fourfold increase in N_1 compared to the scenario without MTD. Interestingly, $P(X)$ and N_1 remain unaffected by the scanning rate or shuffling interval.

An intriguing observation is that, in the worst-case scenario, an attacker may never successfully identify the correct IP or port. Several numerical simulations had been conducted to determine how many full scans are required for a successful attack, when IP Shuffling is implemented. As depicted in Figure 3, the results indicate that, on average, an additional full scan is needed to find the target host with an 87% probability. After a third full scan, the success probability is above 95%. Remarkably, this outcome remains consistent regardless of the scanning rate or shuffling interval. Furthermore, attackers typically halt the scanning process if a full scan yields no results. Consequently, the actual value of shuffling may be the act of discouraging the attacker to rescan the network, when nothing is found with the first full scan.

Fig. 3. Cumulative probability to find a moving host per number of full address-space scans with RHSS6. In contrast to these results, without RHSS6, the first scan is always successful (i.e., 100%).

B. Illustrative Case Study: IPv6 Network with /104 Mask

This section evaluates RHSS6 security gains in a specific scenario by applying the equations from Section V. An IPv6 network with a /104 mask is assumed, and IP and Port Shuffling are enabled. This allows for 16^6 unique addresses. An attacker has gained access to the network and is trying to locate an IPv6 address of a device called `srv-1`. By using $N_1 = \frac{n}{2} = \frac{16^6 - 1}{2}$, the attacker would require 8,388,607.5 attempts on average to locate one of the vulnerable servers. Nmap⁵ estimates a scan of all 65,536 ports to take 21 min. By dividing these 21 min by the number of ports, a scanning of a port takes roughly 0.02 s. The same value is used for the IP scanning operation since the scanning rate is similar to port scanning in that case, as explained above. If RHSS6 is not enabled, the attacker would require 167,772 s or 46.6 h to execute the 8,388,607.5 attempts to scan IP addresses of an undefended network. If only IP Shuffling is activated, it takes 93.2 h, doubling the 46.6 h. This is long but still feasible for an attacker to find, for instance, a server IP address in the network. But if port shuffling is also activated, the attacker must scan 65,536 ports to see if an IP address is communicating. Now, the attacker needs 697.3 y on average to locate the correct IP address and port number. Obviously, the minimum time (i.e., the best-case scenario for an attacker) to locate a server is still 0.02 s.

VI. SUMMARY AND OBSERVATIONS

This work presented a new connection shuffling scheme, namely Randomized Host and Service Shuffling in IPv6 (RHSS6), for MTD in the SDN environment. RHSS6 shows that the much larger IPv6 address space, in combination with changing the ports of the used services, creates the needed obfuscation to slow down attackers. Evidently, this obfuscation also has a negative impact on the performance of RHSS6. The degree of security and performance of the overall system hinges on the particular use case and its associated requirements. The expected success rate of an attacker can be manipulated by the defender selecting address space and port range using the formulas in Section V.

⁵Nmap: the Network Mapper - Free Security Scanner <https://nmap.org/>

Performance and security related results indicate that RHSS6 is applicable for practical use cases. However, further research, e.g., a proof-of-concept, is needed to analyze different factors on the RHSS6 performance. For instance, deciding on a trigger interval depends on QoS requirements, available IP range, time to scan a host, and the number of protected hosts in the network. These parameters are decisive also for a practical deployment is a potential research direction.

Finally, a concern with shuffling is clients should know how to communicate with the shuffled host. This means that for using RHSS6 in a practical network, signaling is needed for distributing dynamic connection information or an existing dynamic DNS implementation is to be extended for saving port numbers in DNS records. However, implementing such a solution is out of scope for this paper.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work was supported partially by (a) the University of Zürich UZH, Switzerland and (b) the Horizon Europe Framework Program's project NETWORK, Grant Agreement No. 101139285 funded by the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research, and Innovation SERI, under Contract No. 22.00642.

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